

Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean

List of different feasible models and their required data for each demo site

VERSION 1.0

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Acronyms

AGRI	AgroInsider
BU	Boğaziçi University
CW	Constructed Wetlands
ESIM	Higher School of Engineering of Medjez El Bab
IDRICA	Idrica
LPM	Living Planet Morocco
MED	Mediterranean
MRB	Mujib River Basin
NbS	Nature-based solution
NVZ	Nitrates Vulnerable Zone
MED	Mediterranean
RSCN	Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature
RSS	Remote Sensing Solutions GmbH
SEMIDE	Euro-Mediterranean Information System on know-how in the Water sector
TdV	La Tour du Valat
TUC	Technical University of Crete
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
UNINA	University of Naples Federico II
UNIPR	University of Parma
UNISS	University of Sassari
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València

Executive summary

The overall objective of the "Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean" (OurMED) project is to design and explore innovative and sustainable storage and distribution systems tightly integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale. This is achieved by the combination of scientific and local knowledge, emerging from new and long-lasting spaces for social learning among interdependent stakeholders, society actors and scientific researchers in eight local and one regional MED demo sites. OurMED calls for a transition from a mono-sectoral water management approach based on trade-offs, to equitable multi-sectoral and integrative management that addresses all water bodies' capabilities and needs towards sustainability.

Milestone 4.2 (M4.2) is part of Task 4.2, which involves assembling a smart modelling portfolio and preparing mitigation scenarios, supporting tailored scenarios and strategies at each demo site. These efforts are intended to enhance adaptive capacity, mitigate the impacts of changing climate conditions, improve ecosystem resilience, promote fair water distribution, and effectively meet stakeholder needs. Specifically, M4.2 aims to create a detailed inventory of all available models, outlining their functionalities and specifying the data they require.

1. Introduction

The “Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean” (OurMED) is an EU-funded project operating under Grant Agreement Number 2222. OurMED aims to design and explore innovative, sustainable storage and distribution systems integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale.

To achieve these objectives, Task 4.2 of the OurMED project is dedicated to assemble a smart modelling portfolio and preparation of mitigation scenarios tailored for each demo site. This task is closely linked with Task 4.1 (see D4.1, Godoy et al., 2024), where the data and tools required to populate multi-sectoral water management indicators and parameters are catalogued and prepared. Additionally, it interfaces with WP3 and WP5, where stakeholder-suggested and nature-based mitigation options are discussed and defined.

Milestone 4.2 (M4.2) is part of Task 4.2. The aim of M4.2 is to identify and list, for all demo sites, the available models and their required data. This report specifically focuses on identifying feasible models able to perform the optimization processes outlined in Task 4.1, and able to test adaptation and mitigation strategies, while considering climate change impacts.

The application of these models, will be detailed in Deliverable D4.2

2. Available models and their data requirement

In the following sections, the available models and their required data, for each demo site, are reported. These models will be instrumental in executing the optimization procedure outlined in D4.1 (Godoy et al., 2024), and are essential for integrating all strategic adaptation and mitigation scenarios identified by WP3 and WP5, also under climate change conditions.

2.1. Bode (Germany)

The characterisation of the Bode demo site was detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). The water policy for the Bode catchment aims to ensure sufficient and high-quality water for various users, including domestic consumption, agriculture, and ecosystem services. Despite substantial investments and efforts, challenges persist, particularly in water use, forest dieback, and the impacts of drought on nutrient leaching and agricultural practices.

To address these issues, the OurMED project focuses on enhancing water distribution and quality during low-flow conditions at the Bode demo site. Two key challenges have been identified through the cooperation of Task 4.1, WP3, and WP5, which need to be addressed by the available models:

- Water quantity: evaluating the potential increase in water availability by utilizing groundwater for irrigation instead of surface water during low-flow periods;
- Water quality: enhancing ecological conditions and controlling nitrate concentrations using innovative water management strategies and nature-based solutions (NbS).

2.1.1. List of available models and their data requirement

mHM-Nitrate model

The mHM¹-Nitrate model (Yang et al., 2018; Samaniego et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2022) is a grid-based fully distributed hydrological and water quality model designed for catchment-scale applications. It simulates surface discharge and nitrate concentration based on widely accepted hydrological conceptualizations, aiming to reproduce discharge hydrographs, soil moisture distribution, and other water-related processes. It incorporates multiscale parameter regionalization, which ensures reliable performance across both gauged and ungauged basins. Within the OurMED project, the model operates at a 1 km resolution.

¹ <https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=40114>

Input data:

1. Meteorological variables:

- Precipitation.
- Average air temperature.
- Potential evapotranspiration: calculated from air temperature using methods like Hargreaves-Samani, Priestley-Taylor, or Penman-Monteith.

2. Morphological variables:

- Digital Elevation Model (DEM).
- Soil properties (sand/clay content, bulk density, root depth).
- Geological data.
- Streamflow location (latitude, longitude).

3. Land cover:

- Land cover maps.
- Leaf Area Index (LAI).

4. Streamflow measurements:

- Streamflow.

5. Groundwater data (optional):

- Groundwater station location and head measurements.

Output data:

The outputs of the model include both nitrate levels and surface water discharge.

MODFLOW model

The MODFLOW 6 model (Langevin et al., 2022) is a fully distributed groundwater flow model, widely used for simulating groundwater levels and flow. The model applies the control-volume finite-difference method to simulate interactions between groundwater and surface water, aquifer storage, and flow through porous media. It is used in both steady-state and transient conditions to manage water resources and assess aquifer dynamics. Within the OurMED project, the model operates at a 200 meter resolution.

This model has been coupled with mHM-Nitrate, where recharge from mHM is used as an input for MODFLOW and river depth is used as a boundary constraint, enabling a comprehensive simulation of groundwater-surface water interactions and their influence on nitrate concentrations.

Input data:

1. Aquifer properties:

- Hydraulic conductivity.

- Specific storage.
 - Specific yield.
2. Boundary conditions:
- River and recharge data: water flow from surface water bodies and precipitation recharge.
 - Head-dependent boundaries: groundwater head, where the flow is driven by the hydraulic gradient.
3. Initial groundwater levels:
- Initial hydraulic head values to set the starting point for the simulation.

Output data:

MODFLOW outputs include groundwater levels. Future groundwater nitrate concentration after MODFLOW and mHM-Nitrate model coupling.

Data-driven model

A data-driven model has been developed to simulate instream water temperature and oxygen concentration using various proxy parameters. The chosen machine learning/deep learning technique identifies complex relationships between the input proxy parameters and the output variables: water temperature and oxygen concentration.

Input data:

1. Proxy variables for water temperature:
- Air temperature.
 - Solar radiation.
 - Precipitation.
 - Wind speed.
 - Relative humidity.
 - Streamflow (discharge).
 - Groundwater inflow.
 - Reservoir releases.
2. Proxy variables for oxygen concentration:
- Water temperature.
 - Nitrate concentration.
 - Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD).
 - Streamflow (discharge).
 - Land use and riparian vegetation.

Output data:

The outputs of the model include instream water temperature and instream oxygen concentration.

Table 1 presents a summary of the available models for the Bode demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 1 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
mHM-Nitrate	Simulate surface discharge and nitrate concentrations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Meteorological variables 2. Morphological variables 3. Land cover 4. Streamflow measurements 5. Groundwater data (optional) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nitrate concentrations. 2. Surface discharge.
MODFLOW	Simulate groundwater levels and nitrate concentration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aquifer properties: 2. Boundary conditions 3. Initial groundwater levels 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Groundwater levels 2. Groundwater nitrate concentration
Data-driven model	Simulate instream water temperature and oxygen concentration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Proxy variables for water temperature 2. Proxy variables for oxygen concentration 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Instream water temperature 2. Oxygen concentration

2.2. Albufera (Spain)

The characterisation of the Albufera demo site was detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). The lake has historically suffered from pollution caused by urban and industrial activities, with untreated discharges continuing despite sanitation efforts initiated in the 1990s. Currently, the lake is hypertrophic, characterised by elevated phytoplankton levels. Regarding water quantity, levels are managed to balance the needs of rice cultivation and the environment, with management practices influenced by drought conditions and agricultural demands. The hydrological cycle is closely tied to irrigation schedules, with gate operations playing a pivotal role in water management. Gates are opened for irrigation from January to March, closed during the rice-growing season, reopened for harvesting, and closed again for winter flooding (the so-called perellonà), which promotes biodiversity and nutrient mineralisation. Despite these environmental considerations, crop production remains the primary priority.

To address the challenges faced by the Albufera Natural Park, the OurMED project focuses on two key issues, identified through the efforts of Task 4.1, WP3, and WP5, which the available models must tackle:

- Enhancing water quality: expanding constructed wetlands (CW) to improve water quality and biodiversity while mitigating nutrient and suspended solid loads from runoff;

- Improving water availability: increasing water availability for perellonà by utilizing additional sources such as groundwater and treated wastewater from local treatment plants.

2.2.1. List of available models and their data requirement

Data-informed model

A data-informed model is being developed to simulate the efficiency of constructed wetlands in improving water quality by reducing nitrogen concentrations. The model uses performance data from existing wetlands (Martín et. al., 2013; Hernández-Crespo et. al., 2017), along with expert knowledge, to identify relationships between wetland characteristics, inflow concentration, and nitrogen levels. This approach enables the optimisation of wetland placement, characteristics, and numbers to maximise water quality improvements.

Input data:

1. Performance data of existing constructed wetlands:
 - Effectiveness of different wetland designs or systems in removing nitrogen.
 - Nitrogen removal rates across various constructed wetlands.
 - Efficiency metrics for nitrogen removal in constructed wetland systems.
2. Hydrological data:
 - Flow rates.
 - Water depth.
 - Hydraulic retention time (which influences the performance of wetlands in treating water).
3. Water quality data:
 - Measurements of nitrogen concentrations in both inflows and outflows from the constructed wetlands.
4. Wetland characteristics:
 - Size.
 - Shape.
 - Vegetation types (which can affect their ability to treat water).

Output data:

The output of the model is the wetland efficiency, expressed as the percentage reduction in nitrogen concentrations, which reflects the effectiveness of the wetland in improving water quality.

AQUATOOL model

AQUATOOL (Andreu et al., 1996) is a decision-support system developed at the Technical University of Valencia for integrated water resource management. It models complex hydrological systems, including surface water, groundwater, and supply networks, under diverse conditions. AQUATOOL features specialised modules for simulating water quantity and quality, with the SIMGES module being the one applied in OurMED. The SIMGES module (Andreu et al., 1992) is designed for simulating the management of river basins and complex water resource systems, incorporating surface and groundwater storage, regulation, capture, transport, usage, and artificial recharge.

Within the OurMED project, the existing AQUATOOL-SIMGES model, originally developed to replicate the functioning of the Albufera system, is being updated to simulate processes aimed at minimising water deficits during the winter flood and maximising water swapping.

Input data:

1. Monthly inflows from various sources:
 - Freshwater from Turia and Jucar rivers.
 - Aquifer.
 - Water treatment plants.
 - Direct precipitation.
2. Hydrological data:
 - SW-GW flux exchange coefficients.
 - Infiltration, (including return flows).
3. Water demand data:
 - Monthly water demands.
 - Prioritisation for different uses.
 - Guarantees for different uses.
4. Reservoir data:
 - Height.
 - Area.
 - Storage volumes and capacity (including those associated with rice paddies).
 - Monthly evaporation.
5. Operational management data (rules for managing reservoirs and water transportation):
 - Seasonal water level targets.
 - Winter flood control.

Output data:

The outputs are provided as total volumes as well as monthly quantities for several components: outflows, which include releases to the lake, outflows to the sea, and system losses; the final volume in each reservoir, including those associated with rice paddies; surface and groundwater supplied; deficits for each demand type; net recharge; and the volume of groundwater pumped.

Table 2 presents a summary of the available models for the Albufera demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 2 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
Data-Informed model	Simulate the efficiency of constructed wetlands in improving water quality by reducing nitrogen concentrations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wetland performance. 2. Hydrological data. 3. Water quality data. 4. Wetland characteristics. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wetland efficiency.
AQUATOOL	Simulate processes aimed at minimising water deficits during the winter flood and maximising water swapping.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monthly inflows. 2. Hydrological. 3. Water demands and priorities. 4. Reservoir parameters. 5. Operational management rules. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Outflows (lake releases, sea outflows, system losses). 2. Final reservoir volume (including rice paddies). 3. Surface and groundwater supplied. 4. Deficit per demand type. 5. Net recharge. 6. Groundwater pumped volume.

2.3. Agia (Greece)

The characterisation of the Agia demo site was detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). This basin is a vital water source for Chania Prefecture, serving agriculture, domestic needs, industrial operations, and tourism. The primary water source is the karst aquifer of Agia, which supplies various wells and springs. Current management of water resources involves regulating extraction from these sources by several governmental authorities. However, excessive water abstraction during dry periods has led to nutrient imbalances and sedimentation in Lake Agia, causing a decline in water quality and availability.

The OurMED project for the Agia demonstration site focuses on improving the equitable distribution of surface water and groundwater among stakeholders. The project identifies two main challenges for analysis based on the work of Task 4.1, WP3, and WP5:

- Preserving Lake Agia's water levels: ensuring sustainable groundwater extraction to support biodiversity and lake restoration;

- Minimizing extraction costs: reducing expenses associated with groundwater extraction.

2.3.1. List of available models and their data requirement

PTC model

The Princeton Transport Code (PTC, Babu and Pinder, 1984) is a numerical simulator that solves a system of partial differential equations in order to represent the subsurface flow, the velocities and the contaminant mass transport in the simulated aquifer. PTC employs a unique splitting algorithm for solving the fully three-dimensional equations, which significantly reduces the computational burden. The algorithm discretizes the domain into approximately parallel horizontal layers and within each layer a finite element discretization is used allowing for the accurate representation of irregular domains. The layers are connected vertically by a finite difference discretization. This hybrid coupling of the finite element and finite difference methods enables the application of a splitting procedure according to which, during any given time iteration, all the computations are divided into two steps: (a) in the first step all the horizontal finite element discretization are solved for each layer, (b) in the second step, the vertical equations which link the layers, are solved using the updated information from the horizontal equation solution.

Input data:

1. Aquifer properties:
 - Hydraulic conductivity.
 - Specific storage.
 - Porosity.
 - Surface topography and elevations.
 - Layer thickness.
 - Dispersivity coefficient in case of contaminant transport.
2. Boundary conditions:
 - First type boundary conditions - Dirichlet (specified head, specified concentration).
 - Second type boundary conditions - Newman (specified water flux, specified mass flux). Pumping wells are treated as second type boundary conditions.
 - Third type boundary conditions - Cauchy (combination of first and second type for groundwater flow and mass transport).
3. Initial groundwater levels:
 - Initial hydraulic head values to set the starting point for the groundwater flow simulation.
4. Initial concentrations:
 - Initial concentration values to set the starting point for the mass transport simulation.

Output data:

PTC outputs include groundwater levels, velocities and contaminant concentration.

Gurobi Optimizer

Gurobi (Gurobi Optimization, LLC, 2024) is used to solve linear programming, quadratic programming, quadratically constrained programming, mixed-integer linear programming, mixed-integer quadratic programming and mixed-integer quadratically constrained programming. Gurobi is a special type of software called a “solver”. The Gurobi interface for MATLAB allows users to create an optimization model, pass the model to Gurobi, and obtain the optimization result - all within the MATLAB environment.

Input data:

1. PTC output:

- The PTC output of the hydraulic heads is used to create a response matrix approach that can pass to the optimization problem in MATLAB environment that uses the Gurobi optimizer.

Output data:

The optimal pumping rates at selected locations that satisfy a multi objective function and a set of hydraulic head constraints.

WEAP model

WEAP ("Water Evaluation and Planning" system), developed by the Stockholm Environment Institute's U.S. Center, is a software tool that takes an integrated approach to water resources planning. It specifically helps in the allocation of limited water resources between agricultural, municipal and environmental uses through full integration of supply, demand, water quality and ecological considerations (Sieber and Purkey, 2015). WEAP's main abilities lie in its capacity to simulate water demand, supply, quality, and allocation under different scenarios. Its flexibility allows for the modelling of a wide range of systems, from urban water supply networks to basin-wide hydrological processes, making it suitable for addressing issues such as climate change impacts, policy evaluation, and sustainable water management.

The WEAP system is being used as part of the OURMED project to improve the management of water resources in the Keritis catchment area. By simulating both historical and predicted hydrological conditions, the system will allow a comprehensive assessment of water availability, demand and distribution. The application of WEAP will also allow the evaluation of different management strategies, including the development of water infrastructure, while providing important insights into the potential impacts of climate change on water resources. Through these simulations, WEAP will generate valuable data and analysis that will support informed decision making and ensure the sustainable allocation and management of water resources in response to current needs and future challenges (Yates et al., 2005).

Input data:

2. Elements:

- Demand nodes.
- Supply nodes.
- Rivers.
- Infrastructure.

3. Demand data:

- Domestic water requirements.
- Agricultural water requirements.
- Population.
- Irrigated areas.
- Consumption rates.

4. Meteorological variables:

- Precipitation (monthly time series).
- Reference evapotranspiration: calculated from air temperature using Penman-Monteith method.

5. Reservoirs:

- Inflow.
- Reservoir storage capacity.

6. Groundwater data :

- Storage capacity.
- Groundwater extraction rates.
- Springs discharge.

7. Land use and land cover:

- Land use maps.

Output data:

The output data of the WEAP includes river discharge and catchment runoff. WEAP also allows the assessment of the impact of climate change on water resources.

SWAT model

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) developed by USDA (U.S Department of Agriculture) is a hydrological model developed to quantify the effects of land management practices on large watersheds. Operating with a daily time step, SWAT can simulate the long-term impacts of such practices on water resources. This publicly accessible model integrates various processes, including hydrology, sediment transport,

and water quality, providing critical insights for effective watershed management (Neitsch et al., 2011)

Input data:

1. Meteorological data:
 - Daily precipitation.
 - Temperature.
 - Relative humidity.
 - Solar radiation.
 - Wind speed.
2. Topography:
 - Digital Elevation Model (DEM).
3. Weather stations:
 - Name.
 - Latitude.
 - Longitude.
 - Elevation.
4. Soil data:
 - Soil type maps or soil classification units.
5. Land use and land cover:
 - Land use maps.
6. Hydrological response unit

Output data:

The surface runoff and the surface hydrological processes.

Table 3 presents a summary of the available models for the Agia demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 3 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
PTC	Simulate groundwater levels and contaminant concentration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aquifer properties. 2. Boundary conditions. 3. Initial groundwater levels. 4. Initial concentrations. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Groundwater levels and velocities. 2. Contaminant concentration.
GUROBI optimizer	Solves the quadratic optimization problem of a multi objective constrained problem	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The PTC output of the hydraulic heads. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Optimal pumping rates.
WEAP	Sustainable water management by simulating water availability, demand, and allocation under various scenarios.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Elements. 2. Demand Data. 3. Meteorological Variables. 4. Reservoirs. 5. Groundwater data. 6. Land use and land cover. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. River streamflow. 2. Catchment streamflow.
SWAT	Assessment of the long-term impacts of land management on water resources for effective watershed management.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Meteorological Data. 2. Topography. 3. Weather Stations. 4. Soil Data. 5. Land use and land cover 6. Hydrological response unit 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Surface runoff. 2. Surface hydrological processes.

2.4. Arborea (Italy)

The characterisation of the Arborea demo site were detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). Since 2005, the area has been designated a "Nitrates Vulnerable Zone" (NVZ), necessitating stringent regulations that pose financial challenges. Water availability for irrigation is not a significant issue, as the Eleonora d'Arborea dam, one of Europe's largest, sufficiently supports all irrigation needs. Groundwater is used for non-drinking purposes, such as livestock washing and industrial processes. Despite the overall adequacy of water availability for irrigation in the Arborea district, significant water quality concerns persist in both surface and groundwater. Several studies have highlighted contamination issues bringing to light the need for targeted modelling to mitigate this behaviour.

In this regard, the OurMED project for the Arborea demo site aims to improve the quality of groundwater and wetlands. The two main challenges identified are:

- Controlling nitrate sources: addressing nitrate pollution in groundwater and wetlands by promoting changes in soil use;
- Enhancing ecological conditions: implementing innovative water management strategies and nature-based solutions (NbS) to control nitrate concentrations and improve ecological conditions.

2.4.1. List of available models and their data requirement

APEX model

The Agricultural Policy Environmental eXtender (APEX) model is a physically-based model that operates on a continuous daily time-step (Gassman et al., 2010). It is versatile and can be used at different spatial scales, from individual fields to small watersheds. APEX's components simulate various processes related to soil dynamics, hydrology, plant growth, carbon and nutrient cycling, livestock grazing, and water-sediment-nutrients routing. One distinctive feature of the APEX model is its ability to divide the simulated area into smaller segments, commonly known as subareas. Each subarea is the smallest simulation unit in APEX and is determined by factors such as landscape position and morphology, soil type, and land use/land management practices. During the simulation, water, along with transported sediment, nutrients, and pesticides, is routed from one subarea to another based on their landscape position. This enables the simulation of water flow from the highest point to the outlet of the simulated area. In the case of the Arborea demo site, these subareas can represent agricultural fields, field borders, and zones with trees growing along the channels.

Input data (input data in bold are essential):

1. Site Information:
 - Latitude and longitude.
 - Elevation.
 - Slope.
 - Field or watershed area.
 - Presence of a reservoir.
 - Drainage system.
 - Water table.
 - Adoption of erosion control practices.
2. Weather data:
 - **Maximum and minimum air temperature.**
 - **Precipitation.**
 - Solar radiation.
 - Relative humidity.
 - Wind speed (measured at 10 meters).
 - CO₂ concentration.
3. Soil characteristics:
 - **Layer thickness.**
 - **Sand percentage.**
 - **Silt percentage.**

- pH.
- **Soil organic carbon percentage.**
- Wilting point.
- Field capacity.
- Organic nitrogen concentration.
- Sum of bases.
- Calcium carbonate content.
- Cation exchange capacity.
- Coarse fragment content.
- Mineral nitrogen concentration.
- Mineral phosphorus concentration.
- Saturated conductivity.
- Lateral hydraulic conductivity.
- Organic phosphorus concentration.

4. Management

- Operations:
 - Date of operation.
 - Type of operation.
 - Tillage depth.
- Fertilization:
 - Type of fertilizer.
 - Application rate.
- Irrigation:
 - Type of irrigation.
 - Amount applied.
- Planting:
 - Plant or crop planted.
 - Plant density.
- Harvesting:
 - Harvester used.
- Grazing:
 - Grazer type.
 - Stocking rate.
 - Beginning and ending day of grazing.
- Pesticide Application:
 - Type of pesticide.
 - Amount applied.

Output data:

The APEX model provides various outputs that represent plant growth and productivity, water flows, soil erosion, nutrient dynamics, and more. Key outputs include water balance components (e.g., evapotranspiration, precipitation, irrigation, runoff, and percolation), crop growth indicators (e.g., total biomass accumulation, above-ground biomass, root biomass, leaf area index, and yield), hydrology metrics (e.g., surface runoff, subsurface flow, and percolation), sediment and nutrient losses (e.g., water-driven sediment, nitrogen, and phosphorus losses, including water-transported mineral and sediment-transported organic fractions, as well as organic carbon losses), and pesticide losses. These results will help to understand the fate of nitrogen and phosphorus transported by water and the impact of land management on their movement to the wetland west of the demo site. The model can also clarify the role and impact of trees growing along the channels and help identify strategies to mitigate nutrient losses in the studied area.

Table 4 presents a summary of the available models for the Arborea demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 4 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
APEX	The APEX model aims to assess the impacts of land management practices on soil, water, and nutrient dynamics across different scales, supporting sustainable agriculture and environmental management.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Site information. 2. Weather data. 3. Soil characteristics 4. Management 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Water balance. 2. Crop growth. 3. Hydrology 4. Sediment and nutrient losses 5. Pesticide losses

2.5. Mujib (Jordan)

The characterisation of the Mujib demo site was detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). The Mujib River Basin (MRB) relies on both surface water and groundwater resources, with groundwater primarily used for drinking and domestic purposes, while surface water supports agriculture and industrial needs. Despite current water management practices addressing both water sources, the MRB faces significant issues of water scarcity and conflicts over water allocation and quality. To address these challenges, different governmental authorities have recommended enhancing water management through improved monitoring, sediment assessment, and the implementation of drought and flood management strategies.

In this context, the OurMED project for the MRB aims to promote integrated river basin management and ensure sustainability for all stakeholders. Two main challenges identified from Task 4.1, WP3, and WP5 are:

- Balancing water allocation: developing strategies to manage water sharing between agricultural and industrial sectors while ensuring ecological flows for the Mujib Reserve;
- Improving water management: evaluating and optimizing water regulation tools for better demand and supply management, addressing issues such as aquifer depletion and exploring alternative water sources.

2.5.1. List of available models and their data requirement

WEAP model

WEAP ("Water Evaluation and Planning" system), developed by the Stockholm Environment Institute's U.S. Center, is a software tool that takes an integrated approach to water resources planning. It specifically helps in the allocation of limited water resources between agricultural, municipal and environmental uses through full integration of supply, demand, water quality and ecological considerations (Sieber and Purkey, 2015). WEAP's main abilities lie in its capacity to simulate water demand, supply, quality, and allocation under different scenarios. Its flexibility allows for the modelling of a wide range of systems, from urban water supply networks to basin-wide hydrological processes, making it suitable for addressing issues such as climate change impacts, policy evaluation, and sustainable water management.

As part of the OurMED project, WEAP will be used to identify the water allocation among the domestic, agricultural, industrial and other sectors in MRB under present and potential future climate change scenarios. Besides, the other objective is to show how the several scenarios such as land use changes, social and economic growth and agricultural development affect water demand and availability. Considering all the input data, which is mentioned below and with several scenarios, WEAP will provide results to ensure the equitable water distribution in MRB. The incorporation of climate projections will further assist authorities in making informed decisions, such as sourcing alternative water supplies from outside the watershed or managing water demand through the adoption of advanced technologies for the future.

Input data:

1. Climate data:
 - Precipitation.
 - Evapotranspiration.
2. Hydrological data:
 - River inflows.
 - Dam storage.
 - Groundwater recharge.
3. Water demand data:

- Domestic.
- Industrial.
- Agricultural.
- Environmental.

4. Water management policies and assumptions.

Output data:

The outputs are the simulated water balances that encompass river flows, dam storage, and groundwater recharge; water allocation maps for demand sites; scenario-based projections on water supply, demand, and climate change impacts; and recommendations for water resource management and policy adjustments.

Table 5 presents a summary of the available models for the Mujib demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 5 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
WEAP model	Sustainable water management by simulating water availability, demand, and allocation under various scenarios.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Climate data. 2. Hydrological data. 3. Water demand data. 4. Water management policies and assumptions. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simulated water balances. 2. Water allocation maps. 3. Scenario-based water supply and demand projections. 4. Policy and management recommendations.

2.6. Sebou (Marocco)

The characterisation of the Sebou demo site was detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). Challenges in the Sebou Basin include water over-exploitation, pollution from agricultural and industrial sources, habitat degradation and ageing infrastructure, all exacerbated by climate change. To address these, an integrated water management strategy is being implemented, focusing on modernizing irrigation techniques, adopting advanced water treatment technologies, and enforcing conservation measures.

For the OurMED project, the focus is on the Moyen Sebou sub-basin, specifically the Dayet Aoua Lake area. Intensive agriculture, particularly apple cultivation, has led to significant groundwater abstraction and reduced lake volumes since 1980. Strategies are being explored to restore the environment of the lake, such as optimizing irrigation systems and encouraging the cultivation of less water-intensive crops. Preliminary results suggest that improved irrigation methods could reduce water use by up to 40%.

The two main challenges identified by other tasks and work packages (Task 4.1, WP3 and WP5) are:

- Maintaining economic activities: ensuring the sustainability of apple orchards while balancing water demands. This includes the integration of innovative agricultural practices that contribute to water conservation and enhance the resilience of the orchards against climatic variability;
- Restoring lake levels: rehabilitating Dayet Aoua Lake to support not only recreational use but also its ecological functions. This involves measures such as recharging the lake using engineered hydrological solutions and implementing stringent regulations to control the inflow and quality of water entering the lake.

2.6.1. List of available models and their data requirement

Hydrological water balance model

To quantify the hydrological inputs and outputs of the Dayet Aoua lake, a hydrological model is available, offering a detailed evaluation of the water balance to inform sustainable water management practices. This model integrates the volumetric balance and water balance equation approaches. The volumetric balance is determined from measured lake levels and topography, while the water balance equation incorporates key components such as runoff, direct precipitation, evapotranspiration, and complementary exchanges (e.g., subsurface flows).

The model operates using historical climate data, hydrological measurements, and land use information to simulate the lake's water dynamics over time. Calculations are performed using a combination of spreadsheet tools and hydrological equations, allowing for the integration of monthly meteorological data (e.g., rainfall, evaporation) with hydrological parameters (e.g., runoff coefficients). While no specialized software is used, the methodology is validated by comparing calculated and observed lake levels.

This approach is particularly suited for assessing seasonal and interannual variations in the lake's hydrology, supporting decisions on sustainable agricultural practices and water management policies.

Input data:

1. Climate data:
 - Rainfall:
 - Over the lake and surrounding catchment areas.
 - Direct precipitation on the lake.
 - Evaporation rates.
2. Hydrological data:
 - Surface runoff.
3. Morphological data:

- Lake surface area.

Output data:

The output data includes calculated water volume changes in the lake, providing detailed insights into the adjustments in volume over time based on the balance of inputs and losses. Additionally, it features estimated water balances over specified periods, offering comprehensive evaluations that are invaluable for analysing trends and informing future planning and management strategies.

HEC-RAS model

To simulate water flow dynamics and lake level changes over time, a 2D hydraulic model of Dayet Aoua will be used, enabling the prediction and management of flood risks while supporting ecological and water resource management strategies. The Hydrologic Engineering Center River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) software is selected for this task. HEC-RAS (Hydrologic Engineering Center, 2021) is a widely used modelling tool designed to simulate the hydraulics of water flow in natural and constructed channels. It allows for detailed analysis of water surface profiles, flow patterns, and inundation mapping, providing essential insights for flood risk management and resource planning.

Input data:

1. Topographic data:
 - Digital Elevation Model (DEM).
2. Hydrological data:
 - Inflow and outflow hydrographs.
3. Environmental data
 - Land use.
 - Soil types.
4. Hydraulic data:
 - Manning's Coefficients for Surface Roughness.

Output data:

The output data includes calculations of water depth at various points, which are important for flood risk and ecological studies, as they provide insights into the lake's spatial variability. Flow velocities, or the speed of water movement at different sections, are also measured, playing a critical role in erosion and sediment transport studies. Additionally, simulated lake levels predict future water levels under various scenarios, providing essential data for operational planning and risk management. An assessment

of potential flood risks is conducted by evaluating areas vulnerable to flooding based on simulated water dynamics, a crucial aspect for effective disaster preparedness.

Groundwater dynamics and piezometry model

To assess the fluctuations in groundwater levels and their impact on Dayet Aoua Lake, a groundwater dynamic and piezometry model is available. This model helps in understanding aquifer health and the interactions between groundwater and surface water systems. This model integrates piezometric monitoring data and hydrological parameters to evaluate aquifer health and the interactions between groundwater and surface water systems. It uses piezometric data collected from field surveys and groundwater level measurements, combined with basic hydrological calculations, to simulate groundwater dynamics and their influence on the lake. This model relies on spreadsheet-based tools and analytical techniques to analyze groundwater flow patterns, recharge rates, and discharge interactions. The methodology includes the interpretation of piezometric maps and time-series data to identify trends and anomalies in groundwater behaviour.

This model provides valuable insights into sustainable groundwater management and its role in the ecological restoration of Dayet Aoua. The findings are supported by data from previous studies, including the Dayet Aoua restoration study (WED, 2022), which serve as a reference for validation.

Input data:

1. Groundwater data:
 - Groundwater level.
 - Aquifer Characteristics:
 - Permeability.
 - Porosity.
 - Aquifer boundaries.
2. Climatic data:
 - Local precipitation.
 - Evaporation rates.

Output data:

The output data includes piezometric levels, which provide detailed mapping of groundwater levels around the lake, aiding in the understanding of groundwater-lake interactions. Groundwater flow patterns are also visualized, offering insights into the direction and rate of groundwater movement, which significantly influences water availability and quality. Additionally, the analysis of the interaction between the lake and the aquifer helps assess the exchange between groundwater and surface water, a crucial factor for managing the water balance and supporting ecological health.

Table 6 presents a summary of the available models for the Sebou demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 6 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
Hydrological Water Balance Model	To quantify the hydrological inputs and outputs of the Dayet Aoua lake.	1. Climate data. 2. Hydrological data. 3. Morphological data.	1. Calculated water volume changes in the lake. 2. Estimated water balance over specified periods.
HEC-RAS	To simulate water flow dynamics and the Dayet Aoua lake level changes over time.	1. Topographic data. 2. Hydrological data. 3. Environmental data. 4. Hydraulic data	1. Water depth. 2. Flow velocities. 3. Simulated lake levels. 4. Potential flood risks.
Groundwater Dynamics and Piezometry Model	To assess the groundwater level fluctuations and their impact on the Dayet Aoua lake.	1. Groundwater data. 2. Climatic data.	1. Piezometric levels 2. Groundwater flow patterns 3. Interaction between the lake and the aquifer.

2.7. Medjerda (Tunisia)

The characterisation of the Medjerda demo site was detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). The basin faces water scarcity due to increased demand and decreased water flow, with recent flows averaging less than 40% of the historical average.

Within the Medjerda basin, two sub-catchments are highlighted: Bouhertma and Siliana. The Bouhertma sub-catchment supports regional drinking water supply, irrigation, and flood prevention. The Siliana sub-catchment operates primarily for irrigation and flood control. Water management in the Medjerda basin faces challenges including conflicts over water use, siltation, and climate change impacts.

As part of the OurMED project for the Medjerda demo site, the aim is to enhance water resource allocation and support sustainable surface water management. Two key challenges have been identified from the interdependent work carried out from Task 4.1, WP3, and WP5:

- Surface water allocation and use efficiency: enhancing water supply and developing guidelines for land use and land cover;
- Policy support for sustainable management: addressing conflicts over water sharing between upstream and downstream users.

2.7.1. List of available models and their data requirement

SWAT Model

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT), developed by the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA), is a semi-physically distributed hydrological model designed to quantify the effects of land management practices on large watersheds. Operating with a daily time step, SWAT can simulate long-term impacts on water resources by integrating various processes such as hydrology, sediment transport, and water quality (Neitsch et al., 2011). This publicly accessible model is well-suited for capturing spatial and temporal variability in precipitation, climate, soil properties, and land use to simulate flow (Arnold et al., 1998). It uses Hydrological Response Units (HRUs), which represent unique combinations of land use, soil type, and slope at the sub-catchment scale, to model rainfall-runoff processes. By requiring spatial and temporal inputs, SWAT can draw a water balance at catchment or sub-catchment scales and has been widely applied to assess hydrological processes under various environmental conditions, including the impacts of climate change.

As part of the OURMED project, the SWAT model is applied to the Siliana sub-catchment (El Ghoul et al., 2023) to assess water availability under climate change projections and evaluate the siltation rate of the dam.

Input data:

1. Digital Elevation Model (DEM):
 - Overlay of the real hydrographic network.
 - Slopes.
 - Flow directions.
 - Drained surfaces.
 - Hydrographic and stream network.
 - Determination of the watershed delineation.
2. Soil properties:
 - Number of layers.
 - Soil hydrological class.
 - Soil depth.
 - Texture.
 - Bulk density.
 - Hydraulic conductivity.
 - Water soil content at wilting point and field capacity.
 - Soil rock content.
 - Soil erodibility.
3. Land use data:

- Cropped land.
- Pastureland.
- Forest.
- Urban.

4. Climate data:

- Precipitation.
- Temperature.
- Wind.
- Solar Radiation.
- Relative Humidity.

5. Discharge.

Output data:

The output data includes water availability under current and future climate scenarios, providing insights into potential changes in water resources due to climate variability. Additionally, it evaluates the siltation rate of the dam, quantifying sediment accumulation over time, which is crucial for understanding the impact on reservoir capacity and long-term water management.

HYPE model

The HYPE model is a hydrological model for small-scale and large-scale assessments of water resources and water quality, developed at the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute during 2005–2007 (Lindström et al., 2010). The HYPE model can be used for predictions in un-gauged basins for scenario modelling and climate change impact assessment. The model calculates surface discharge, evapotranspiration, storage of snow and the molten, soil moisture, fluctuations of groundwater. The watershed can be divided into sub-basins. Each sub-basin can be divided into classes, according to soil type and land use, which are the smallest computational spatial unit and defined as Soil Land Classes (SLCs).

As part of the OURMED project, the HYPE model is applied to the Bouhertma sub-catchment to assess surface discharge and estimate the expected water resources.

Input data:

1. Meteorological data:

- Daily precipitation.
- Daily temperature (Average, min, max).
- Potential evapotranspiration (calculated from air temperature using Hargreaves-Samani method).

2. Hydrological data:

- Daily discharge.
3. Morphological data:
- Digital Elevation Model (DEM).
 - Mean Slope.
 - River network.
 - Flow Direction.
 - Sub-basins boundaries.
 - SLCs.
4. Soil properties:
- Sand content.
 - Clay content.
5. Gauge and meteorological station location:
- Latitude.
 - Longitude.
6. Land Use Land Cover classification.

Output data:

The output data includes the expected water resources.

Table 7 presents a summary of the available models for the Medjerda demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 7 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
SWAT	Simulate flow and erosion	1. Digital Elevation Model 2. Soil properties 3. Land use 4. Climate data 5. Discharge	1. Water availability considering climate change projection 2. Siltation rate of the dam
HYPE	Simulate surface discharge	1. Meteorological data 2. Hydrological data 3. Morphological data 4. Land cover	1. Expected water resources

2.8. Konya (Turkey)

The characterisation of the Konya demo site was detailed in D2.1 (Koroptsenko et al., 2024). The relatively low precipitation (about 350 mm/year), high water demand of the agricultural sector, inefficient irrigation practices, and excessive groundwater extraction have led to severe stress on both surface and groundwater resources. Even with some

measures already implemented, water demand in severe drought scenarios is projected to decrease significantly.

At this demo site, the surface water distribution system prioritizes domestic water demands, followed by irrigation needs, with any surplus allocated for ecological services, such as restoring dried wetlands.

As part of the OurMED project for the Konya demo site, the goal is to promote sustainable water resource management and balance between upstream and downstream users in the Lake Beyşehir zone. Two key challenges have been identified for analysis using the outcomes obtained from different work packages (Task 4.1, WP3, and WP5):

- Surface water allocation and groundwater pumping: assessing the allocation and supplementary pumping requirements to support biodiversity and wetland restoration;
- Policy support for sustainable management: aiding policy-making processes for sustainable surface water resource management, focusing on conflicts over water sharing between upstream and downstream users.

2.8.1. List of available models and their data requirement

WEAP model for surface water allocation

WEAP ("Water Evaluation and Planning" system), developed by the Stockholm Environment Institute's U.S. Center, is a software tool that takes an integrated approach to water resources planning. It specifically helps in the allocation of limited water resources between agricultural, municipal and environmental uses through full integration of supply, demand, water quality and ecological considerations (Sieber and Purkey, 2015). WEAP's main abilities lie in its capacity to simulate water demand, supply, quality, and allocation under different scenarios. Its flexibility allows for the modelling of a wide range of systems, from urban water supply networks to basin-wide hydrological processes, making it suitable for addressing issues such as climate change impacts, policy evaluation, and sustainable water management.

As part of the OurMED project, WEAP will be used to allocate the available water resources of the Konya closed basin by balancing competing demands, namely by integrating environmental considerations alongside human needs for domestic use and agriculture. As described below data from different sources will be incorporated into the WEAP model. Moreover, its open-ended architecture also supports customization and integration with other tools like MODFLOW for groundwater modelling.

Input data:

1. Surface water distribution network
2. Meteorological data:
 - Monthly precipitation.
 - Monthly temperature.
 - Reference evapotranspiration.

3. Land-use data:

- Agricultural area (irrigated & rainfed).
- Distribution of different crops.
- Crops coefficient (Kc) for determining agricultural water demand.

4. Hydrological data:

- Historical water level (volume and elevation) for lakes and dams in the basin.
- Historical groundwater water level.
- Storage capacity and initial storage of lakes and dams.
- Evaporation from the surface of lakes and dams.
- Channel flows.

5. Socio-economic data:

- Population growth rate.
- Annual water use rate.

6. Water demands:

- Water transfers.
- Water treatment for domestic use.
- Ecological water demands (targets for maintaining ecological services).

Output data:

The outputs are the changes in lake and dam levels, discharges in monthly monitoring, and groundwater level changes.

MODFLOW model

The MODFLOW model (Langevin et al., 2022) is a fully distributed groundwater flow model, widely used for simulating groundwater levels and flow. MODFLOW is a process-based model that solves the groundwater flow equation which is derived based on the principle of conservation of mass. The model simulates the flow of groundwater using the finite-difference method considering all groundwater sources and sinks. The model can be used to simulate steady state as well as transient flow.

As part of the OurMED project, the groundwater flow model is defined to cover the entire Konya closed basin. The MODFLOW version coupled with the UZF1 (Unsaturated Zone Flow) Package, developed by the United States Geological Survey (USGS), is used for this demo site. The coupled MODFLOW/UZF1 Model simulates vertical water flow through the vadose zone along with saturated flow in the underlying aquifer system. The processes that are simulated with the UZF package are infiltration and evaporation in the vadose, along with vertical flow. The UZF1 package simulates flow in the vadose zone based on the kinematic wave equation, a simplified version of Richards' equation. An advantage of the coupled system is that it does not require to define the net recharge

into the aquifer. Instead, the net recharge is one of the main outputs of the model and is transferred to the groundwater flow simulator MODFLOW.

Input data:

1. Aquifer properties:
 - Hydraulic conductivity.
 - Specific storage.
 - Specific yield.
2. Vadose zone properties:
 - Unsaturated zone flow parameters.
 - Porosity.
 - Monthly evapotranspiration potential.
3. Boundary conditions:
 - No flow boundaries across the Konya closed basin boundaries
4. Initial groundwater levels:
 - Initial hydraulic head values to set the starting point for the simulation.
5. Hydrological Data:
 - Historical groundwater water level.

Output data:

The outflow from the coupled MODFLOW/UFZ1 model includes net aquifer recharge and groundwater levels.

Table 8 presents a summary of the available models for the Konya demo site, detailing their functionalities, data requirements, and corresponding outputs.

Table 8 Type of available models, input data and provided output.

Model	Aim	Input data	Output data
WEAP	Sustainable water management by simulating water availability, demand, and allocation under various scenarios.	1. Surface water distribution network 2. Meteorological data 3. Land-use Data 4. Hydrological Data 5. Socio-economic Data 6. Water transfers	1. Water levels in reservoirs. 2. Groundwater levels
MODFLOW/UFZ1	Simulate groundwater and vadose zone flows	1. Aquifer properties 2. Vadose zone properties 3. Boundary conditions 4. Initial groundwater levels 5. Hydrological Data	1. Aquifer recharge to aquifer. 2. Groundwater levels

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